

HOW TO IMPROVE READING SKILL OF PUPILS EFFECTIVELY IN ENGLISH CLASSES AT SCHOOL.

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ABSTRACT: This article discusses the ways of reading skills and what kinds of approaches help pupils to settle difficulties that they have. Because more and more pupils and students in various levels and classes want to gain good results in their education by the help of the knowledge about reading skills and other skills which they use that's why they need new methods to achieve their target goal in short time through new and easy approaches about four skills: listening, reading, writing, speaking. But you know reading is basic skill for other threes. Because if you want to know any information in books or electronic programs in your laptop, you desire to find and get data in short time and effectively so this article open this kind of sides of reading comprehension for you. And also teachers may use tips in this article to improve the reading skills of their pupils in auditory. Because researchers have found that teaching reading strategies is a key element in developing student comprehension.

Key words: reading skills, approaches, strategy, important aspects of reading, scanning, predicting.

Introduction.

Nowadays more and more people especially young generation are keen on learning any other languages out of their languages. And we know all of languages consist of four skills: reading, writing, speaking and listening. But we especially get new data by reading so reading is a lifelong skill to

be used both at school and throughout life. According to Anderson, Hiebert, Scott, & Wilkinson, reading is a basic life skill. It is cornerstone for a child's success in school and indeed throughout life. Without the ability to read well, opportunities for personal fulfillment and job success inevitably will be lost (1985). But reading skill is one of the difficult area in learning languages. Because some people don't understand what they read during their life when they read any books, newspapers, magazines and so on. Because it is just difficult for them to comprehend information by their reading comprehension in their brain. So Teele asserts that the goal of all readers should be to understand what they read. (2004). So every teacher help their pupils to improve comprehension through instruction of reading strategies: predicting, visualizing, making connections, inferring, questioning and summarizing. Because any kind of language skills includes 2 group of skills like receptive skills and productive skills. And also our language skills like reading, writing, speaking, listening come into these two skill groups. For example: listening and reading are receptive skills. Because we just to get written information by the help of receptive skills that they have already created by other people, like listening and reading. But productive skills that we create ourselves .new something. So that speaking and writing are productive skills. Because we always create our speech and our text by ourselves. So that we face up difficulties while we learn reading skills affectively. But some ways help as to understand any text that we are reading easily. If we divide them according to the natural order of the language listening and speaking are primary skills and reading and writing are secondary, because every normal human can listen and speak first, then they learn skills of writing and reading. In language teaching and learning, all four skills play a vital role to get mastery over language.

TEACHING OF READING SKILL

Teaching of reading is an important aspect of teaching language. Reading skill is one of four language skills which come under receptive skill. Reading is a

process of communication from the writers to the readers. It involves re-organization of printed letters, words, phrases, clauses in some aspect. It can be considered a simple process rather than comprehension. It is a process of understanding a text in its simple sense, understanding a text means comprehending a text. Thus, reading is the total understanding of message or text. There are several skills in teaching reading. It means reading includes a variety of skills. Teaching reading skill incorporates following sub-skills:

- a. Recognition of script
- b. Deducing the meaning / unfamiliar lexis.
- c. Understanding implicit things
- d. Understanding the communication value
- e. Relation between sentences
- f. Interpreting the text
- g. Identifying the main point. Skimming / scanning
- i. Predicating
- j. Sensitizing.

PREDICATION

Predication is a skill used by teacher to train students guess what is coming next in the reading passage. This is not really a technique but a skill which is basic to all the reading techniques. It is the faculty of predicting or guessing what is to come next, making use of grammatical, logical and cultural clues. Its specific aim is to train students to make predictions and guess when reading a text. Predicting is very necessary because reading is an activity involving constant guesses that are later reject or confirmed. This means that one does not read all the sentences in the same way, but one relies on a number of words or cues to get an idea of what kind of sentences is likely to follow.

SCANNING

Scanning is a strategy used in reading to find out the particular piece of information from the text. Scanning is a strategy of reading that refers to the rapid

survey of a text to find out particular piece of information. Grellet (1981) defines scanning as, Scanning, on the contrary, is for more limited since it only means retrieving what information is relevant to purpose. When scanning, we only try to locate specific information and often we do not even follow the linearity of the passage to do so. It is said that reading is a silent and personal activity which does not imply that it only lends itself to individual work. On the contrary, it is particularly interesting to encourage comparison between several interpretation of a text which will lead to discussion and probably a need to refer back to the text to check

SKIMMING.

Skimming is a reading technique to find out the gist of the text. Skimming is a reading activity which means quickly going through the text to find out the gist of it. Grellet (1981) defines skimming as a more thorough activity which requires an overall view of the text and implies a definite reading competence." When skimming, we go through the reading materials quickly in order to get gist of it, to know how it is organized or, to get an ideas of the tone or the intention of the writer.

DEDUCING THE MEANING.

Deducing meaning is a process that we guess the meaning of any kind of unfamiliar lexis from the text that we are reading by the help of our knowledge, or we understand the meaning of unfamiliar words by the help of other words or following words in the text.

IDENTIFYING THE MAIN POINT OF THE TEXT.

We always pay attention main points and meaning of text, while we are reading any texts like, article, story, novel, news and so on. If we want to know what kind of theme was described in a text. First of all, we look at the title of the text, because it help us to know what kind of theme is about in the text. We know, when we read a title of any text, we usually organize a lot of idea in our mind about a text. And then if this text is necessary for us we continue reading this

information or text. So that we should choose short and understandable title for our text. As well as we should describe all of meaning of text by our title. This is a main point. Because if we choose incorrect or uninteresting title for text or our article. No one reads this article, although this text is helpful for these people. And then all information in a text should become in a good order. Because while readers are reading this text. They must not face up intricacy. This is a main point of writing helpful articles for readers. Next main point is planning or abstract of the text or article. Because they give data for us about main side of text. And which categories that writer is going to describe and so on. That's why reading comprehension and improving reading skill is very important for all people. Because human can pay attention to main side and know how to find main point of article or text, he or she does not have to read all information in the text.

TEACHERS ROLE OF IMPROVING PUPILS' READING SKILL

In order to comprehend and ultimately enjoy reading a text, a reader be engaged in it. It is a difficult task to make students engage with texts. Malin (2010) says “to encourage all students to become readers, they need to assume the creative attitudes and literate behavior of engaged readers. To be able to reflect on a reading event, engaged readers need to first decode, then comprehend, and finally transact with the text to construct meaning. However, unengaged readers are often unable to reflect on their reading as a result of lack of interest, poor reading skills, limited comprehension strategies, or lack of personal experiences to use, and construct meaning.”Malin (2010) assures that the educational and aesthetic value of a particular digital video reading aid can help the students engage in reading literature and he suggests that this reading solution can not only engage students in the text but also help them comprehend, critically analyze and enjoy the reading experience as a whole. When students do not see anything when they read, they cannot think about or experience the text. Jacob (1976) found that the major difference between good and poor readers was their ability to use imagery during a reading. Eisner (1976) says that the image-visual, tactile, auditory plays a crucial

role in the construction of meaning through text. Those who cannot imagine cannot read. It is possible that non-engaged readers can be encouraged to enter into story world and, in turn become engaged readers. As Enciso (1990) posited, mental imagery or visualization of a story has many powerful positive effects for readers and is vital for comprehension, engagement, and response.” Nowadays most of students, pupils, older generation especially young people want to learn English language, because it is the language of the world. And they want to enter universities in English - speaking countries. So they try to get special certificates like IELTS, TOEFL, CAE, CPE . Everyone knows in these testing systems have reading section. So every candidate has to solve or find answers of questions of given passage in a given time. But time is limited and short. That's why time is not enough for candidate to catch up with all three passage to read and solve, if they don't know some strategies or way to find answers to the passages. So teachers who prepare students to IELTS examination often teach their students some ways like, scanning, skimming, deducing, guessing, for helping students to economize time and find answer easily from text to question not to read whole text. So more and more students gain good results from the exam by the help of teachers and methods that teachers teach.

READING SKILL THROUGH MULTIMEDIA

Multimedia enables the students learn reading autonomously. They can be given enough training through some activities. Driscoll (2008) emphasizes skimming and scanning of many things can be done through websites. Nowadays computers play a major role in assisting reading. There are diverse programs of reading instruction that sound favorable involving computers. Using of computer and other technologies are ways of guiding students in learning reading. Marlow Edger thinks that there are numerous means of utilizing personal computers in teaching students in the area of reading (Sharma & Sharma 2006). Abundant software packages help the students to improve their reading skill. Some software packages give drill and practice if students face difficulties in learning reading. At

the most basic level, reading is sometimes thought to consist of translating symbols on a page, or on a computer screen, into sounds, in what is sometimes referred to as 'barking print'. Some people would argue that it isn't reading at all. But it is clear that there is more reading than merely being able to perform a neat trick of vocalizing sounds that are represented by the symbols (Fairbrain & Fairbrain, 2002). A host of multimedia options help students develop critical reading skill in both decoding and comprehension (Cooper, 2008). Students may select to read a library book whereby the recorded voice is contained in a cassette directly related to the printed words. As the cassette or CD ROMS plays the sequential words, they may follow along in their own chosen book (Ediger & Rao, 2004). In this kind of activity students gain an increasing number of sight of words for reading as well as increasing skill in reading. This way of reading facilitates the students identify new words and comprehend the content read. The recorded voice helps the pupils to grasp ideas which would not be possible without recording. This will also eliminate individualized reading difficulties. Teachers can give phonemic drills to the students with rich AV aids, PowerPoint slides and Snapshots.

NEWSPAPERS IN TEACHING READING.

The variety of subjects and topics makes newspapers interesting and motivating for students to work with. Newspapers report real-life events, and this arouses students' curiosity. Newspaper-based activities in the classroom may engage students in enjoyable activities and encourage them reading further. As newspaper is an invaluable source of authentic material, it creates interest among them and that leads to motivate them. Motivation leads to more reading. The more students read, the more they explore. "People learn through reading, and reading about interesting new things in one's interesting subject, undoubtedly helps motivation" (Sanderson, 2002:). Newspapers are also a great source for educators. They can be used as teaching materials to develop students' language skills. They can be used effectively with a wide range of levels from elementary to advanced, either interpreting them or using them as they are. Some newspapers are easy to

read, easy to use. Committed teachers can design exercises to develop reading comprehension, critical thinking skills, writing skills, grammar skills, vocabulary, map/chart reading skills, geography skills, social study skills and more. Having a lot of newspapers and information, teachers should be careful with the way how to organize a certain activity and using them. So, they are particularly suitable for mixed-ability classes, depending on the activity, questions, etc. Planning a lesson, using a newspaper, a teacher should take into consideration the length of the article, paragraph, the complexity of the language, the density of the information, subject-matter and content, time available and levels of students. Students should cultivate reading habit so as to be enriched with the knowledge of the diction, pronunciation, phrase, different structures and vocabulary. This is an era of rapid technological changes in mass communications. Through internet, students can access thousands of newspapers and magazines worldwide. Internet has increasingly become a major source of newspapers and magazines for language teachers. But they should be very careful in choosing a suitable newspaper, materials to use with their students (Tafari, 2009).

CONCLUSION.

In my conclusion. Reading skill is a basic skill for learning languages. Because most of information that we take, knowing by reading text version from a book, magazine, newspaper or social networks. So reading skill is necessary for all humans during their life. That's why people must organize this skill well in their school years. So teachers role is important for improving students reading comprehension and reading skill in school year. That's for All of teachers always become active and should choose a right way for a pupil's age. And they become friendly, kind, creative, energetic, polite, knowledgeable. Because if teachers have this characters they can explain every side of improving reading skill for their children. Because I also experienced these ways to my pupils. And I chose a suitable way for my pupils age and level at school. As well as I achieved good results.

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